

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP and IWG9

Deliverable 2.3 Insights on EU and national
support instruments for CCUS R&I and
deployment

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordination and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

Disclaimer

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1.1 Introduction

This report builds on deliverable 4.1 under the IMPACTS9 project published in April 2022 and follows a similar structure¹. The objective of this report is to provide an overview of the various research and innovation programmes available at the EU and national level for the deployment of carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) in Europe. This overview is coupled with insights into the structure and priorities of national R&I programmes in selected countries (Denmark, France, Germany, Sweden, and the UK). Research organisations and project developers that are planning to develop R&I projects on CCS and CCU can use this report to identify available funding programmes. This report also provides recommendations to policymakers to improve R&I efforts targeted at CCS/CCU deployment.

The publication of the industrial carbon management strategy, the proposed EU 2040 climate target, and the expected agreement on the Net Zero Industry Act create strong ambitions for CCS and CCU in view of reaching climate neutrality²³. The Net Zero Industry Act is expected to create an objective of 50 million tonnes of CO₂ per year injection capacity in the EU by 2030. The strategy forecasts that 280 million tonnes of CO₂ per year would have to be captured in the EU by 2040, at least 250 million tonnes of CO₂ per year stored geologically in the European Economic Area (EEA) in 2040, and up to 450 million tonnes of CO₂ per year captured in the EU by 2050. These forecasts are aligned with the scenarios developed under the 2040 EU climate target proposed by the European Commission and imply consequential efforts to develop large-scale transport and storage infrastructure across Europe. A report by the Joint Research Centre, developed for the strategy, estimates that the cost of the European CO₂ transport network could cost up to €12.2 billion by 2030⁴. This last figure shows that very significant funding efforts are needed to ensure CCS's deployment and reach climate neutrality. The role of research and innovation is key to reaching these objectives. R&I programmes will help ensure that the most effective technologies are deployed along the value chain and that the most up-to-date information is available to policymakers, project developers, and all stakeholders involved in the deployment of CCS.

1.2 Contributors

This report built on the previous report 'Report on opportunities for joint programming of R&I funding for CCUS' developed by Marie Bysveen (SINTEF). Several interviews were conducted to gain a better insight of national R&I programmes dedicated to CCS and CCU. The authors would like to acknowledge contributions from Anja Fink (Agency for energy and climate protection in North Rhine-Westphalia), Sebastian Fischer (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action), Carol Paquier (French Ministry of Ecological Transition), Marine Plassier (French Ministry of Ecological Transition), Jeppe Sabroe Thegen (Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities), Svante Söderholm (Swedish Energy Agency), and Aage Stangeland (Clean Energy Transition Partnership). The report includes insights based on discussions with these contributors. The report only reflects the authors' view and not those of these contributors or the organisations they work for.

¹ <https://ccus-setplan.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/4.1.pdf>

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2024%3A62%3AFIN&qid=1707312980822>

³ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2ccd7710-5fc3-420f-aeb8-9a3af271f970_en

⁴ <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/e5aad873-4a75-4c74-8014-eace0a7d4781>

1.3 Acknowledgments

This report is a deliverable in the Horizon Europe project SSZEPIWG9⁵, supporting the SET Plan Action 9 on CCUS⁶. This report builds on earlier recommendations and reports from IMPACTS9 and in particular the report 'Report on opportunities for joint programming of R&I funding for CCUS' drafted by Marie Bysveen (SINTEF) and published in April 2022⁷.

1.4 Disclaimer

This document reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission and CINEA are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

1.5 Background

During this decade, it is crucial to put in place the policy and regulatory framework for the large-scale deployment of CCS and CCU technologies in view of reaching the CCS/CCU deployment targets for 2030, 2040, and 2050 and reach climate neutrality by 2050. While the mitigation role of CCS is acknowledged in the industrial carbon management strategy, significant funding efforts are required to reach the targets set. Funding for CCS/CCU R&I plays an important role in this picture, as research and innovation will help develop the most effective technologies to reach these targets.

1.6 EU policy developments and their impact on R&I

The European Commission published the industrial carbon management strategy, the first EU strategy on CCS and CCU, and a Communication on an EU 2040 climate target on 6 February 2024^{8,9}. The strategy forecasts the following:

- 50 million tonnes of CO₂ per year captured in the EU by 2030;
- approximately 280 million tonnes of CO₂ per year captured in the EU by 2040;
- up to 450 million tonnes of CO₂ per year captured in the EU by 2050;
- by 2040, about half of the captured CO₂ would come from biogenic sources or from the atmosphere; and
- at least 250 million tonnes of CO₂ per year stored geologically in the European Economic Area in 2040.

⁵ <https://www.ccus-setplan.eu/about-impacts9/>

⁶ <https://www.ccus-setplan.eu/>

⁷ [Report on opportunities for joint programming of R&I funding for CCUS](#), CCUS SET Plan, April 2022.

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2024%3A62%3AFIN>

⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2024%3A63%3AFIN>

Figure 1: Volume of CO₂ captured for storage and utilisation in the EU (above chart) and share of the CO₂ captured by origin (below chart)¹⁵

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The Joint Research Centre published the report “Shaping the future CO₂ transport network for Europe”, which shows that “the future European CO₂ transport network could reach a length of 6,700-7,300 km by 2030, and might extend to between 15,000 and 19,000 km by 2050. Its deployment could cost between about €6.5 billion and €19.5 billion by 2030, rising to between €9.3 billion and €23.1 billion in 2050”¹¹.

Figure 31. Scenario D2 - Fit-for-55 & NZIA 2030 targets (EU), year 2030

Source: JRC, 2024

¹⁰ Industrial carbon management strategy, European Commission, 2024.

¹¹ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC136709>

The strategy also states that the Commission foresees to “boost EU research, innovation and early-of-a-kind demonstration for novel industrial technologies to remove CO₂ under Horizon Europe and the Innovation Fund” and “continue to invest in R&I for industrial carbon management technologies, including 24 energy and cost efficiency optimisation of processes and pre-normative research to contribute to standardisation”. This would imply additional R&I funding for carbon removals and preserved funding for CCS/CCU standardisation. The CCUS Forum report ‘An Interoperable CO₂ Transport Network – Towards Specifications for the Transport of Impure CO₂’ recommends to policymakers to “develop as rapidly as possible a network code and standards for a multimodal CO₂ transport network in the EU/EEA” and to support and prioritise research in a number of fields¹², including the following:

- potential interactions between several different compounds in the CO₂ stream (for example the stabilisation of aqueous phases by polar molecules);
- prediction of phase transitions and the accompanying partitioning of the impurities into the new phases and non-equilibrium phase transition conditions, in the context of multi-component systems;
- chemical reactions of impurities within the CO₂ stream;
- fundamental research on chemical reactions paths and kinetics;
- prediction of the mass flow and the composition in two-phase flows;
- dynamics of a pipeline network for CO₂ containing impurities for dense phase transport;
- the impact of extended two-phase regions on operational procedures for pipeline transport in the dense phase;
- challenges resulting from solid phase formation and operational procedures for pipeline pressures above about 2 MPa for transport at gas states;
- energy-efficient technologies for heating up CO₂ streams;
- practical limits regarding the flexibility of mass flows into storage reservoirs;
- risks linked to chemical reactions that could result from the mixing of different impurities from different CO₂ streams; and
- the design of facilities to process the landed CO₂ that could be captured from the exhaust gas of ships.

The Council and the European Parliament found a provisional agreement on the proposal for a regulation Net Zero Industry Act on 6 February 2024. A leaked version published by Contexte on 12 February 2024 indicates that the regulation could include “measures aimed at supporting innovation through the creation of net-zero regulatory sandboxes, coordination of research and innovation activities through the Strategic Energy Technologies Plan Steering Group, as well as through the use of pre-commercial procurement and public procurement of innovative solution”. A net zero regulatory sandbox is defined as a ‘scheme that enables undertakings to test innovative net-zero technologies and other innovative technologies in a controlled real-world environment, under a specific plan, developed and monitored by a competent authority’. This would include “adapting existing regulatory practices and using their discretionary powers when implementing and enforcing legal provisions to a specific net-zero regulatory sandbox project, with

¹² <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/75b4ad48-262d-455d-997a-7d5b1f4cf69c/library/13c2a475-c705-432d-8ca3-17ce799ba502/details>

the objective of removing barriers, alleviating regulatory burden, reducing regulatory uncertainty, and supporting innovation in net-zero technologies or other innovative technologies”. CCS and CCU technologies would be eligible to these regulatory sandboxes. Finally, the Act would create a SET Plan Steering Group to “provide guidance and direction to the Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan” and “support the development of clean, efficient and cost-competitive energy technologies through coordination and collaboration in clean energy research and innovation”.

Ahead of the publication of the proposed Net Zero Industry Act in 2023 ZEP published a paper stating “the importance of strengthening the support for CCS and CCU research and innovation (R&I), given that this is the very foundation to achieve efficient and fit-for-purpose solutions. ZEP recommends following the proposals made by the SET Plan CCUS implementation working group (IWG9)”¹³.

The Council and the European Parliament found a provisional agreement on the proposal Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform on 16 February 2024. The European Commission proposal included an increase in Horizon Europe of €500 million for the 2021-2027 period¹⁴. ZEP published a statement on 29 January 2024 to “support the European Commission’s proposal for a regulation Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP) that proposes to increase the size of the Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe funding programmes”¹⁵. However, this proposed increase is not included in the provisional agreement and no increase in the Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe is foreseen.

An increase in R&D efforts for CCS and CCU is required in view of the significant deployment targets for CCS and CCU required by the industrial carbon management strategy and the EU 2040 climate target. These recent policy developments highlight a mismatch between the large-scale deployment of carbon capture that is quickly required to reach net-zero by 2050, and the R&I funding available that would ensure that the latest knowledge and technologies are available to support such deployment.

1.7 EU funding mechanisms for CCUS R&I

1.7.1 Horizon Europe

Horizon Europe¹⁶ is the largest research and innovation funding programme in the world¹⁷ and a major source of public funding for CCS/CCU in Europe, where CCUS is included in the Cluster 'Climate, Energy and Mobility'. The EU's R&I programme Horizon Europe has a budget of €95.5 billion for the 2021-2027 period. The Horizon Europe work programme 2023-2024 topics was prepared in consultation with Member States on CCS/CCU and CDR including CO₂ transport, utilisation, and storage and direct air carbon capture and storage (DACCS) and bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS).

¹³ [ZEP paper on the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act](#), 2023.

¹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52023PC0335>

¹⁵ <https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/zep-statement-step/>

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/strategy_on_research_and_innovation/presentations/horizon_europe/ec_rtd_he-investing-to-shape-our-future.pdf

¹⁷ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/worldwide/india/horizon-europe-largest-ri-program-world-officially-launched>

In the work 2023-2024 programme the following topics belong to the wider ‘Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS)’ theme:

- HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-17: Development of CO₂ transport and storage demo projects, with an indicative budget of €40 million with the selected project “expected to use the CO₂ from one or more capture sites and build or use a transport infrastructure, incl. shipping if needed, to the selected storage site where the CO₂ will be injected”
- HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-18: Clean Energy Transition Co-funded Partnership: with an indicative budget of €71 million (see below for a more detailed description of the Partnership)
- HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-01: Development of near zero-emission biomass heat and/or CHP including carbon capture, with an indicative budget of €8 million with the selected project expected, among others, to “enhance the sustainability of biomass-based heat and/or CHP by addressing socioeconomic and environmental sustainability, in particular in reducing emissions and air pollution and also addressing aspects of carbon reuse and circularity, also in particular in fossilfuel-based economic areas in transition”
- HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-11: CCU for the production of fuels, with an indicative budget of €15 million with the selected project expected to contribute to the “development of energy-efficient and economically and environmentally viable CO₂ conversion technologies, including energy storage and/or displacement of fossil fuels that allow for upscaling in the short to medium term”
- HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-12: DACCS and BECCS for CO₂ removal/negative emissions, with an indicative budget of €15 million with the selected project expected to contribute to “improve existing or develop new materials for DACCS and/or BECCS technologies or address potential barriers to the incorporation of DACCS and/or BECCS technologies in existing CC(U)(S) concepts or make DACCS and/or BECCS technologies a viable option to make the EU carbon neutral by increasing the TRL levels and reducing cost of the different technological options”.

1.7.2 Partnerships

ERA-NET ACT

A main pillar for joint public funding of CCUS R&I in Europe is the partnership ERA-NET Accelerating CCS Technologies (ACT)¹⁸. ACT had several calls for RD&D projects in the period 2016-2023. However, there will no new ACT call. The ACT Consortium has the ambition of continuing the collaboration as part of the Clean Energy Transition Partnership¹⁹.

Clean Energy Technology Partnership (CETP)

The Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) aims to empower the energy transition and contribute from a R&I perspective to the EU's goal of becoming a climate-neutral continent by 2050. CCS and CCU is one of the areas described in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)²⁰. The CETP proposal was approved by the European Commission in December 2021.

¹⁸ <http://www.act-ccs.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://www.act-ccs.eu/calls>

²⁰ https://eranet-smartenergysystems.eu/global/images/cms/CETP/CETP_SRIA_v1.0_endorsed.pdf

The research challenges identified in CETP have been bulked in 8 Transition Research Initiatives (TRI). The CCUS activities in the CETP will mainly be within (TRI3)- *'Enabling climate neutrality with storage technologies, renewable fuels and CCU/CCS'* and is also described as an important part of the TRI6 – *Integrated Industrial Energy Systems*. The CETPartnership Joint Call 2023 was the second annual co-funded call under the CETPartnership. The call is structured into 12 modules, including 'CM2023-04: Carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS)'. All participating countries, except for Austria, participate in this module. The module "intends to fund projects that aim to accelerate CCUS technologies in support of global efforts to reduce CO₂ emissions by more than 50 percent by 2030 compared to 1990 and further efforts for climate neutrality"²¹.

Insights gathered hereafter are based on information directly provided by the Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP)²².

A new CETP programme has been launched with a new call. The deadline was 22 November 2023. The CETPartnership Joint Call 2023 has an international part and a regional/national part. The third transition initiative (TRI) 'Enabling Climate Neutrality with Storage Technologies, Renewable Fuels and CCU/CCS' is dedicated to CCS and CCU. A new call will take place in 2024. The work will start in January 2024, will be completed in April 2024, and published in May 2024. The due date is November 2024 for proposals, which will be followed by proposals. The 2024 call is expected to be similar to 2023. The 2023 budget for the CETP call was €130 million covering all call modules. The budget for the 2024 call is expected to be similar. The CETP call 2022 resulted in 10 new CCS/CCU projects that will receive in total €22 million in support from the CETP funding agencies.

No statistics are yet available on the different countries involved in CETP. The countries with the most CCS/CCU projects are Norway, the Netherlands, Germany, the United States, Sweden, and Italy. The total funding allocated for 2024 will be decided in Q1 2024. Germany is expected to have a very ambitious CCS strategy that will focus on high technology readiness levels (TRLs) and should not include too much efforts on R&D. There were 46 projects in 2023 and 10 for CCS/CCU, which is considered a very good share compared to other technologies. The focus of the CCS/CCU value chain is to be discussed. There is usually a wide scope for eligible projects and the scope is expected to be very broad in 2024.

Project partners apply for national funding and national research programmes are coordinated via the CETP. Some countries have funding for all modules, some only for certain modules. Norway has prioritised CCS/CCU and district heating with significant funding in 2023. Consortia have to follow national research agencies criteria when they apply for funding. It appears that the national criteria can be confusing for applicants in certain cases. The coordination/harmonisation of these criteria could be useful for effective R&I efforts on climate technologies, including CCS/CCU. The CETP has ongoing discussions with Mission Innovation (MI) to find synergies. One proposal is that MI countries join future CETP calls in 2025.

²¹ <https://cetpartnership.eu/cm2023-04-carbon-capture-utilisation-and-storage-ccus>

²² <https://cetpartnership.eu/>

1.7.3 Innovation Fund^{23 24}

The Innovation Fund is one of the largest funding support schemes funded by credits from the EU ETS²⁵ in Europe for pre-commercial projects in the areas of renewable energy, energy efficiency, energy storage, CCS and CCU. An increasing carbon price means an increasing size of the Innovation Fund. Decreases in the EU ETS price in Q1 2024 led to an analysis suggesting that, a price of €60 per tonne would reduce the size of the programme from €40 billion to €32 billion amounting to a 20% cut²⁶.

The IF has a funding envelope of €40 billion for the 2020-2030 period based on a carbon price of €75 per tonne of CO₂. €6.5 billion have been awarded to 104 projects across the European Economic Area²⁷. Informal exchanges indicate that more funding is required under the Innovation Fund but that existing funding mechanisms, and the cohesion between those, need to be significantly improved to avoid a fragmented and incoherent funding approach.

The third IF call for large-scale projects opened on 3 November 2022. The call results publication took place in July 2023 with grants awarded and project development assistance taking place in Q4 2023. 41 projects amounting more than €3.6 billion were selected for grant preparation out of 239 applications sent. CCS/CCU projects were eligible under this call. 11 CCS/CCU projects were selected, including the GeZero full-chain CCS project at the Geseke cement and plant in Germany, the IFESTOS CCS project at a cement and concrete plant in Greece, the IRIS carbon capture project at a refinery in Greece, the KODECO cement in Croatia, the Everest lime plant in Germany, the GO4ZERO clinker plant in Belgium, e-methanol production at the eM-Rhone project in France, e-methanol production at the Columbus project in Belgium, e-methanol production at the Green Meiga project in Spain, e-methanol production at the Triskelion project in Spain, and the CFCPILOT4CCS hydrogen pilot in the Netherlands. More than 25% of successful applicants are therefore in the CCS/CCU category. Cement, lime, and e-methanol projects are particularly successful in this category²⁸. A view of the projects' geographical spread can be found hereafter.

²⁴ https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/innovation-fund_en

²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets_en

²⁶ Informal analysis from the EU think-tank Bruegel, Politico Pro newsletter, 19 January 2024.

²⁷ https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/innovation-fund_en

²⁸ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-funding-climate-action/innovation-fund/calls-proposals/large-scale-calls/projects-selected-grant-preparation_en

The third Innovation Fund call for small-scale projects opened in March 2023. The call results were published in December 2023 with grants award and project development assistance expected in Q2 2024. 17 small-scale projects amounting to €65 million were selected²⁹. 1 selected project is focused on CCS/CCU: the CUSTARD project in Italy aiming to CCU technology to capture the flue gases of a steel plant for sodium bicarbonate production³⁰.

The Innovation Fund 2023 Call (IF23) is divided into 5 topics associated with different CAPEX requirements: large-scale projects, medium-scale projects, small-scale projects, cleantech manufacturing for components, and pilot projects. The three first and fifth topics cover CCS and CCU (see graph below).

Innovation Fund 2023 Call		
Topic	Project eligibility CAPEX	Sectors covered
Large-scale projects	CAPEX > €100 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annex I and Annex III to the EU ETS Directive 2003/87, including CCU CCS Renewable energy and energy storage technologies Maritime and aviation
Medium-scale projects	€100 million > CAPEX > €20 million	
Small-scale projects	€20 million > CAPEX > €2.5 million	
Cleantech manufacturing for components	CAPEX > €2.5 million	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renewable energy installations Electrolysers and fuel cells Energy storage solutions Heat pumps
Pilot projects	CAPEX > €2.5 million	Validating, testing and optimising highly innovative, deep decarbonisation solutions in all sectors eligible for Innovation Fund support

²⁹ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-funding-climate-action/innovation-fund/calls-proposals/small-scale-calls_en

³⁰ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/pages/innovation-fund-projects-pre-selected-grant-agreement-preparation-following-third-call-small-scale_en

IF23 opened on 23 November 2023 and will close on 9 April 2024. Information on the call results is expected in Q4 2024. The grants are expected to be awarded in Q1 2025, together with project development assistance. Grant funding supports up to 60% of the project's cost. Project selection is based on the following criteria: effectiveness of greenhouse gas emissions avoidance, degree of innovation, project maturity, replicability, and cost efficiency.

1.7.4 Connecting Europe Facility for Energy (CEF-E)

The Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) supports the development of interconnected trans-European networks in the fields of transport, energy, and digital services. For CO₂ infrastructure projects having gained the status of European Projects of Common Interest (PCI) or European Projects of Mutual Interest (PMI), funding is available under the CEF for Energy (CEF-E). This funding stream is connected to the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), and for the 2021-2027 period the budget available under the CEF-E is €5.84 billion.

Selection criteria can be found under Article 4 of the TEN-E regulation, revised in 2022. A project must be necessary for at least one of the energy infrastructure priority corridors and areas and involve at least two Member States to become PCI. A project must contribute significantly to the decarbonisation objectives of the EU and those of the third country involved to become a PMI. The overall benefits of the project must always outweigh its costs³¹.

14 CO₂ infrastructure projects were announced at the CCUS Forum in Aalborg (Denmark) in 2023 and included in the 1st PCI/PMI list³²:

³¹ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ganda_23_6048

³² https://energy.ec.europa.eu/publications/annex-first-union-list-projects-common-and-mutual-interest_en

- 1) CO2TransPorts³³
- 2) Aramis³⁴
- 3) ECO2CEE
- 4) Bifrost³⁵
- 5) Callisto³⁶
- 6) CCS Baltic Consortium³⁷
- 7) Delta Rhine Corridor³⁸
- 8) EU2NSEA³⁹
- 9) GT CCS Croatia
- 10) Norne⁴⁰
- 11) Prinos⁴¹
- 12) Pycasso⁴²
- 13) Northern Lights⁴³
- 14) Nautilus CCS

1.7.5 Important Projects of Common European Interest (IPCEI)

There are no IPCEIs for CCS and CCU at the moment. The industrial carbon management strategy states that “the Commission foresees to work, as of 2024, with Member States in the transparent and coordinated design of a possible important project of common European interest for CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure via the JEF-IPCEI”⁴⁴. An IPCEI for CO₂ transport and storage would allow member states to direct state aid funding to this project⁴⁵.

1.7.6 Other partnerships and funds

The urgency of the climate crisis and the need to meet the UN Sustainable Development Goals (including the EU Taxonomy for sustainable finance) has resulted in different kinds of private-private and public-private partnerships and funds. This represents an important opportunity for CCUS RD&D funding too.

*Mission Innovation*⁴⁶

Mission Innovation is a global initiative aimed at catalysing action and investment in research and development in the field of low-carbon energy to accelerate progress towards the Paris Agreement goals and pathways to net zero. The Carbon Dioxide Removal Mission aims to enable carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies to achieve a net reduction of 100 million metric tons of CO₂ per year globally by 2030.

³³ <https://www.porthosco2.nl/en/>

³⁴ <https://www.gasworld.com/aramis-ccs-project-aims-for-large-scale-carbon-reduction/2021701.article>

³⁵ <https://bifrost-ccs.com/>

³⁶ https://ccushub.ogci.com/focus_hubs/ravenna/

³⁷ <https://ccs-baltic.eu/>

³⁸ <https://www.delta-rhine-corridor.com/en>

³⁹ <https://www.equinor.com/energy/smeaheia>

⁴⁰ <https://norneccs.com/en/>

⁴¹ <https://www.energean.com/operations/greece/prinos-co2/>

⁴² <https://www.pycasso-project.eu/en/home/>

⁴³ <https://northernlightsccs.com/>

⁴⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2024%3A62%3AFIN>

⁴⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A12008E107>

⁴⁶ <http://mission-innovation.net/about-mi/overview/2021-joint-launch-statement/>

The European Commission is part of the Mission Support Group. As part of this Mission, the Carbon Dioxide Removal Launchpad is an initiative to support CDR pilot-scale tests and demonstration projects, with six countries committing to fund at least one CDR project that removes 1,000+ metric tons of CO₂/year by 2025. Participating countries contribute to a collective goal of \$100 million for CDR pilots and demonstrations by 2025. ZEP has provided input and supports the work of Mission CDR via its Temporary Working Group (TWG) CDR. Recent support included identifying and describing mature large-scale CDR projects in the EU for the Launchpad.

EU-Catalyst partnership⁴⁷

The EU-Catalyst partnership is a partnership between the European Commission, the European Investment Bank and Breakthrough Energy Catalyst (Gates Foundation) to mobilise up to €820 million between 2022 and 2026 to accelerate the deployment of innovative technologies. Each euro of public funds is expected to leverage three euros of private funds within in four sectors: clean hydrogen; sustainable aviation fuels; direct air capture; and long-duration energy storage.

European Commission Executive Vice-President Maroš Šefčovič, the founder of Breakthrough Energy Bill Gates, and European Investment Bank President Werner Hoyer announced on 1 December 2023 at COP28 in Dubai the first two European projects that should be supported by the EU–Catalyst partnership: Ørsted's FlagshipONE and Energy Dome's Ottana CO₂ Battery. Ørsted's FlagshipONE is a relevant project for CCS/CCU as it aims to produce 5,000 tonnes of e-methanol per year using renewable hydrogen and CO₂ captured from the biomass-fired combined heat and power plant Hörneborgsverket in Sweden⁴⁸.

Carbon Management Challenge (CMC)⁴⁹

The Carbon Management Challenge is an international initiative launched at the Major Economies Forum on Energy and Climate (MEF) in April 2023. Participating countries agree to advancing CCS, CCU, and CDR projects to collectively capture 1 gigatonne of CO₂ by 2030 to limit global warming to 1.5°C. Participating countries include Denmark, Iceland, the Netherlands, Norway, Iceland, Sweden, and the European Commission as a representative of Member States that are not individually represented⁵⁰. These countries can expand research funding for CCS and CCU as part of the initiative.

Carbon Sequestration Leadership Forum (CSLF)⁵¹

This is a Ministerial-level international CCS technologies initiative, including aspects of awareness, legal, regulatory, financial, and institutional environments relevant to CCS technologies. Participating countries include Czechia, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, the UK and the European Commission as a representative of Member States that are not individually represented. The 2023 Technical Group Mid-Year Meeting took place in Warsaw (Poland) and focused on sharing

⁴⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_21_5586

⁴⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_6169

⁴⁹ <https://www.carbonmanagementchallenge.org/cmc/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.carbonmanagementchallenge.org/cmc/frequently-asked-questions>

⁵¹ <https://www.csforum.org/csrf/>

“knowledge and experiences from CCS and CCU activities and projects in operation, in development or in plans, with a special focus on the potential of Central and Eastern Europe”.

The meeting included presentations and panel discussions on R&D activities, capacities, and competences, and on building CCS and CCU infrastructure⁵².

ECCSEL Research infrastructure⁵³

ECCSEL is a European research infrastructure, providing open access to over 80 facilities in 5 countries, for researchers worldwide. ECCSEL ERIC member countries include France, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, and the UK. ECCSEL opened a Geo-INQUIRE Transnational Access call on 16 January 2024 running until March 2024⁵⁴. The five available research facilities for this call include the Svelvik CO₂ Field Lab, the PITOP Borehole Geophysical Test Site, the Sotacarbo Fault Laboratory, the CATLAB CATenoy experimental site and gas-water-rock interactions LABORatory in Oise, and the MobSeis Mobile Seismic Array⁵⁵.

Recent workshop and conference presentations include an ECCSEL European CCUS Workshop in May 2022, an ECCSEL workshop for industry and academia in June 2023, and a roundtable on creating societal & environmental impact through research & innovation at the EU Sustainable Energy Week⁵⁶.

EEA grants and Norway Grants⁵⁷

The EEA and Norway Grants are funded by Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway. The Grants have two goals – to contribute to a more equal Europe, both socially and economically – and to strengthen the relations between Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway, and the 15 Beneficiary States in Europe (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia). Norway Grants include all 15 EEA Grants beneficiaries, except Greece and Portugal.

The website of EEA Grants highlights a difference in research and innovation performance across the EU Member States and identifies the following challenges⁵⁸:

- underinvestment in research;
- uneven performance in EU framework programmes, where more recent EU Member States have a lower success rate;
- lack of support for young researchers; and
- a gap in innovation efforts.

An evaluation of bilateral cooperation in the EEA and Norway Grants was carried out between March 2023 and September 2023 to assess the effectiveness and sustainability of the current setup and work related to bilateral cooperation. The report points out that there are “examples of project partnerships that led partners to collaborate beyond the Grants scheme. For example, research institutes from Donor and

⁵² <https://fossil.energy.gov/archives/cslf/Events/Warsaw2023.html>

⁵³ <https://www.eccsel.org/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.eccsel.org/news/first-geo-inquire-transnational-access-call-is-open/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.geo-inquire.eu/transnational-access>

⁵⁶ <https://www.eccsel.org/knowledge/workshop-conference-presentations/>

⁵⁷ <https://eeagrants.org/>

⁵⁸ <https://eeagrants.org/topics-programmes/innovation-research-education-and-competitiveness/research>

Beneficiary States jointly apply for the Horizon 2020 funding”. Another finding is that “sustainability largely depends on the sector. Some sectors, e.g. research and innovation, are more suited than others, as there is an already established international element”⁵⁹.

1.8 National strategies and funding for CCUS R&I

More information is presented for the countries that are the most active/with the largest budgets in CCS/CCU R&I: Norway, Netherlands, UK, Germany, France, Denmark, Sweden, and France. Most of the insights gathered hereafter are based on information directly provided by national officials.

1.8.1 Norway

Norway has an internationally strong technological community in the field of CCS and has, for decades, safely operated the CO₂ storage projects on the Sleipner and Snøhvit fields. Norway has large ambitions for CCS deployment, including via the Longship project.

*CLIMIT programme*⁶⁰

Norway has allocated €16 million for funding of research and innovation of CCS in 2022. This budget is made available for the CLIMIT programme, administrated by Gassnova and the Research Council of Norway. A new CLIMIT programme plan was launched in January 2022⁶¹. The main updates are:

- Clear emphasis on realisation of gains of Longship
- A new focus area is the decarbonisation of industrial and energy resources
- Hydrogen production, combined with CCS is a top priority
- Increased focus on direct air capture and bioenergy combined with CCS
- A clearer position of social scientific research

The CLIMIT R&D project portfolio should include 49 projects in 2024 divided between 5 categories: cross-cutting, capture, transport, underground, and end-user. Funding would amount to 329 million NOK or approximately €29 million. The CLIMIT Demo portfolio should include 84 projects in 2024 divided between 4 categories: cross-cutting, capture, transport, and underground. Funding would amount to 388 million NOK or approximately €34 million⁶².

Projects for the 2023-2027 period can be found on the project bank. One project example is “Sharing and recycling shale mechanical data to enable gigaton CO₂ storage” that “aims to improve mechanical integrity assessment of shale formation by providing enhanced approaches to maximize the utilization of shale mechanical data and regional correlations to accelerate maturation of new sites”⁶³.

⁵⁹ <https://eeagrants.org/resources/evaluation-bilateral-cooperation-eea-and-norway-grants>

⁶⁰ <https://climit.no/en/>

⁶¹ <https://climit.no/en/news/climit-has-a-new-programme-plan/>

⁶² <https://climit.no/en/projects/>

⁶³ <https://prosjektbanken.forskingsradet.no/en/project/FORISS/344380?Kilde=FORISS&distribution=Ar&chart=bar&calType=funding&Sprak=no&sortBy=date&sortOrder=desc&resultCount=30&offset=0&Ar=2024&Ar=2023&ProgAkt.3=CLIMIT-Forskning%2C+utvikling+og+demo+av+CO2-h%C3%A5ndtering>

1.8.2 Netherlands

SDE++ subsidy scheme

The Stimulation of Sustainable Energy Production and Climate Transition (SDE++) subsidy scheme^{64,65} in the Netherlands is intended for companies and organisations that produce sustainable energy or apply CO₂-reducing techniques. The scheme finances the unprofitable part of the technology that amounts to the difference between the market value of the final product and the cost of the technology. Subsidies are granted for periods of 12 or 15 years⁶⁶. The total budget amounted to €13 billion in 2022⁶⁷.

Support for CCS/CCU can also be found through the following programmes:

- the Missiegedreven Onderzoek, Ontwikkeling en Innovatie (MOOI) scheme;
 - innovation plans focused on climate action
 - open from 19 March 2024 to 5 September 2024
 - total budget of €61,050,000
- the TSE Industrie studies scheme;
 - pilots or demonstration projects in industry
 - open from 3 April 2023 to 31 March 2024
 - total budget of €20,000,000
- the “TSE Industrie Onderzoek & Ontwikkeling (O&O)” scheme;
 - R&D for cheaper, climate-neutral and/or circular products and services
 - open from 3 April 2023 to 9 May 2024
 - total budget of €1,900,000
- the “DEI+: Energie- en klimaatinnovaties” scheme; and
 - demos, pilots or tests to save energy or reduce CO₂ emissions
 - open from 21 November 2023 to 29 August 2024
 - total budget of €141,000,000
- the “Hernieuwbare Energietransitie (HER+)” scheme.
 - innovative projects focused on CO₂ reduction
 - opened from 3 April 2023 to 31 August 2023
 - total budget of €30,000,000

1.8.3 UK

The UK climate and industry policies have developed rapidly in recent years. In 2020, a ten-point plan was launched, which was further updated with the Net-Zero Strategy⁶⁸ late 2021.

The British Geological Survey (BGS) is developing a storage research facility, funded by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC). The intention is to fund research at low to mid TRLs. In June 2023,

⁶⁴ <https://business.gov.nl/subsidy/sustainable-energy-production/>

⁶⁵ <https://bellona.org/publication/the-industrial-ccsupport-framework-in-the-netherlands>

⁶⁶ <https://english.rvo.nl/subsidies-financing/sde/features>

⁶⁷ <https://english.rvo.nl/sites/default/files/2023-08/English%20brochure%20SDE%2B%2B%202022%20-%20juli%202022.pdf>

⁶⁸ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1033990/net-zero-strategy-beis.pdf

NERC stated that due to high operating costs, NERC was unable to develop this option on its own. At the moment an outline business case has been finalised and frozen⁶⁹.

IDRIC

In order to support the development of CCUS, commercial frameworks are currently being developed and are due to be published in 2022. They are expected to be based on a Contracts for Difference model to complement current renewable frameworks. The UK Industrial Decarbonisation Research and Innovation Centre (IDRIC) is a UK research organization focused on industrial decarbonisation.⁷⁰ IDRIC is part of the £170 million Industrial Decarbonisation challenge and is backed by £20 million funding until 2024. IDRIC has launched its first 40 research and innovation projects.

Projects are grouped into 9 Multidisciplinary Integrated Programmes (MIPs), each addressing a key challenge or pathway for industrial decarbonisation (with some themes, e.g. hydrogen or CCS/CCU, or policy and social aspects, covered in more than one MIP). MIP6 is entitled 'Accelerating CCUS deployment of CCUS for industrial decarbonisation', and includes the following projects:

- MIP 6.1. Accelerating the deployment of cost-competitive advanced carbon capture technologies for industrial decarbonisation
- MIP 6.2 Thermodynamic models for application in industrial decarbonisation
- MIP 6.3. Advanced multitemporal modelling and optimisation of carbon dioxide transport and storage networks
- MIP 6.4. Carbon Dioxide Stored 2.0 - Next generation of the UK's carbon dioxide storage database Research Programmes
- MIP 6.5 Protective space and social licence to operate industrial decarbonisation
- MIP 6.6 Process Intensification of CO₂ Capture with Bioenergy Using Rotating Packed Bed
- MIP 6.7 Algae-based carbon capture and utilisation for UK cluster decarbonisation
- MIP 6.8 AMICUS: Analysis Methods for Improved Capture Using Solvents

Funding opportunities under IDRIC are described hereafter.

⁶⁹ Presentation made at the CCSA Subsurface & Storage Task Subgroup in October 2023.

⁷⁰ <https://idric.org/>

	FLEXIBLE FUNDING	IMPACT ACCELERATOR	SECONDMENT
AIM	Emerging research areas	Impact acceleration of existing IDRIC projects	Support skill development and knowledge exchange industrial decarbonisation stakeholders
DURATION	1-9 months	1-9 months	1-9 months
TOTAL FUND	£1,800,000	£200,000	£500,000
FUNDING AVAILABLE PER PROJECT	Up to £100,000	Up to £30,000	Up to £50,000
COSTS COVERED	Project costs	Project costs	Seconded salary, travel and subsistence
ELIGIBILITY	Funding must be awarded to UKRI-eligible organisation	Funding must be awarded to UKRI-eligible organisation. Applicants must be a named researcher on a IDRIC Wave 1 or 2 research project	Funding can be awarded to any organisation at 80% FEC.
CALL OPEN	Yes	Yes	Yes
CALL CLOSES	See rolling call closing dates below	See rolling call closing dates below	See rolling call closing dates below

Net Zero Innovation Portfolio

The Net Zero Innovation Portfolio is a €1.17 billion fund to support the commercialisation of low-carbon technologies in power, buildings, and industry. Advanced carbon capture, usage and storage (CCUS) is one of the 10 priority areas. This programme is the successor of the BEIS Energy Innovation Programme (EIP) that ran from 2015 to 2021. The CCUS priority area aims to “bring down the cost of capturing and sequestering CO₂ and helping UK industry to understand the opportunity for developing and deploying next generation carbon capture technologies from 2025”⁷¹. This includes the ACT3 initiative providing “up to €5.84 million in grant funding up until 31 March 2025 for CCUS developers to expand on their research and development to push their technologies to higher technology readiness levels”⁷² and the Carbon Capture, Usage and Storage (CCUS) Innovation 2.0⁷³. Both programmes were published in 2022. Another competition under the Net Zero Innovation Portfolio is the ‘Direct Air Capture and other Greenhouse Gas Removal technologies’ that is focused on CDR deployment⁷⁴. This competition was published in 2020.

1.8.4 Germany

Germany is currently developing a national industrial carbon management strategy. The strategy was expected in 2023 but is expected to be published in Q1 2024 instead. High TRL R&I related to CCS and CCU is funded by different state programmes and by the federal ministry for economy & climate protection (BMWi). The largest programme is the “7th Energieforschungsprogramm⁷⁵”, which was followed by an 8th programme in 2023⁷⁶. The 7th programme focused on CO₂ capture and the 8th programme makes no reference to CCS/CCU.

⁷¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/net-zero-innovation-portfolio>

⁷² <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/accelerating-carbon-capture-and-storage-technologies-act-3-grant-funding-winners/grant-funding-winners-accelerating-carbon-capture-and-storage-technologies-3>

⁷³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/carbon-capture-usage-and-storage-ccus-innovation-20-competition-call-1-successful-projects>

⁷⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/direct-air-capture-and-other-greenhouse-gas-removal-technologies-competition>

⁷⁵ https://www.bmwi.de/Redaktion/DE/Publikationen/Energie/7-energieforschungsprogramm-der-bundesregierung.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=16

⁷⁶ <https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Publikationen/Energie/8-energieforschungsprogramm-zur-angewandten-energieforschung.html>

A new smaller scheme called ‘Bundesförderung Industrie und Klimaschutz’ (BIK – ‘Federal funding programme for industry and climate protection’) is expected to include CCS/CCU and could be put forward in March/April 2024. No funding range is available at this stage. The BIK would focus on capital expenditure and would be funded at 70% from the federal level and 30% from the state level. A Carbon Contracts for Difference scheme could also be put forward in 2024 and would cover CCS/CCU. This scheme would be initially limited and would grow over time. The total size of this scheme could range between €30 billion and €50 billion. The scheme would fund both capital and operational expenditure over a period of 15 years.

North Rhine Westphalia (NRW) is a key region for industry in Germany with a turnover of industrial companies around €1.8 trillion in 2019⁷⁷. NRW plans to publish a funding programme in Q1 2024 dedicated to CCU and developed by the Ministry of Economic Affairs, Industry, Climate Action and Energy of North Rhine-Westphalia. This programme aims to address the ‘valley of death’ between research and implementation and to support the integration of existing technologies in a value chain to increase the overall TRL within the process. The TRL is not defined at this stage. The name of the programme is ‘CCU-Modellregionen in Nordrhein-Westfalen’ (CCU model regions in NRW) and would focus on CCU. The priorities for NRW on CCS policy is building the transport infrastructure and defining the quality of CO₂ (specifications). In 2021, NRW had developed a strategy for carbon management⁷⁸. Here, the origin of the CO₂ is key to determine its utilisation. NRW distinguishes hard-to-abate and unavoidable emissions and sees a role for CCS for unavoidable emissions.

1.8.5 France

France’s PEPR (Programme et équipements prioritaires de recherche – priority research programmes) ‘Sous-sol, bien commun’ research programme has a €71.4 million budget over a 7-year period⁷⁹. The programme leaders are the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) and the French geological survey BRGM. France’s industrial investment programme ‘France 2030’ has a €5 billion budget to deploy mature decarbonisation technologies. This programme includes 2 calls for projects related to innovation: DEMIBaC and IBaC PME⁸⁰. Each call has a €120 million planned budget to finance demonstrations and pilots. CCS is one of the 4 priorities of this programme. The DEMIBaC call focused on TRLs from 6 to 9 and IBaC PME had no specific TRL. Both calls closed in October 2023.

The PEPR Spleen is dedicated to industrial decarbonisation and focuses on TRLs below 5⁸². The budget revolves around €70 million, and CCS is one of the identified topics. The 4th investment programme for the future (PIA 4) is included in the France 2030 programme and focuses on mature technologies. CCS is not

⁷⁷ <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/en/industry-production/overview>

⁷⁸ <https://www.wirtschaft.nrw/carbon-management-strategie-nrw>

⁷⁹ <https://www.brgm.fr/en/programme/subsurface-common-good-research-programme-responsible-sustainable-use-exploitation>

⁸⁰ <https://agirpoulatransition.ademe.fr/entreprises/aides-financieres/20230606/developpement-briques-technologiques-demonstrateurs-realizations>

⁸¹ <https://agirpoulatransition.ademe.fr/entreprises/aides-financieres/20220203/developpement-briques-technologiques-services-decarbonation-lindustrie>

⁸² <https://anr.fr/fr/detail/call/pepr-spleen-pour-la-decarbonation-de-lindustrie-appel-a-projets-2024/>

included in PIA 4 at the moment but could be included for hard-to-abate emissions in the future. The France 2030 programme rates proposals based on their technological maturity. Proposals are ranked on their emission reduction efficiency compared to available funding (EUR/CO₂). This factor accounts for 70% of the grade. For proposals with a budget over €30 million, Carbon Contracts for Differences (CCfDs) are currently envisaged.

France published its strategy on CCS/CCU in June 2023⁸³. The strategy includes the following elements:

- A CCUS deployment trajectory, in terms of implementation timetable and volumes of CO₂ emissions captured, based on prioritisation by major industrial zone: first the major industrial ports of Dunkirk, Le Havre and Fos-sur-Mer, then Lacq/South-West and Loire-Estuaire, and finally Grand-Est ;
- A support scheme via Contracts for Difference (CCfD) awarded by call for tender to support CCS projects;
- A CO₂ transport infrastructure framework regulated by the Commission de Régulation de l'Energie (CRE);
- Diversification of CO₂ storage possibilities: before the end of 2023, the government will launch a call for tenders for geophysical exploration campaigns and CO₂ injection tests at pilot sites, with the first tests scheduled for 2024/2025; and
- CCU to decarbonise the aviation and maritime sectors.

The strategy is expected to be finalised in Q1 2024.

1.8.6 Denmark

Innovation Fund Denmark is a programme funding innovative projects in Denmark. This programme has 7.1 billion DKK or €0.95 billion in active investments, close to 2,000 active projects, and received 2,298 applications in 2022⁸⁴. This programme has 4 Missions, including the INNO-CCUS Mission that supports CCS and CCU for building materials. INNO-CCUS is overseen by the Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science and has 5 dedicated workstreams: Chemical CO₂ capture, Biological CO₂ capture and storage, Geological CO₂ Storage, CO₂ utilisation, and Society and Systems Analysis⁸⁵ and more than 80 partners⁸⁶. Partners also have funding programmes that research projects can apply for. More than 30 projects are supported under INNO-CCUS. DKK 80 million or €10.73 million will be distributed to INNO-CCUS projects. The maximum investment per project is DKK 10 million or €10.73 million. The minimum investment per project is DKK 3 million or €10.73 million. A call was opened in January 2023 with the projects expected to be launched in Q4 2023. Projects must have a secured co-financing of at least and must start at least at TRL 3 and reach a maximum of TRL 7 in the project period⁸⁷.

⁸³ <https://www.conseil-national-industrie.gouv.fr/actualites/consultation-sur-la-strategie-nationale-ccus>

⁸⁴ <https://innovationsfonden.dk/en>

⁸⁵ <https://inno-ccus.dk/projects/>

⁸⁶ <https://inno-ccus.dk/meet-our-partners/>

⁸⁷ <https://inno-ccus.dk/call-for-projects/>

INNO-CCUS published the first edition of its 'State of CCUS' report in November 2023⁸⁸. The report provides an exhaustive description of research projects supported for CCS and CCU under this programme. This includes:

- 13 projects in CO₂ capture with a total budget of €42.169 million;
- 29 projects in CO₂ storage with a total budget of €99.6 million;
- 30 projects for CCU with a total budget of €111,660 million; and
- 10 projects in societal coupling with €10.488 million.

The Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Program (EUDP) is run by the Danish Energy Agency and aims to demonstrate new energy technologies, including CO₂ storage⁸⁹. The EUDP programme was created in 2007 and has supported more than 1,200 projects with about DKK 6.2 billion or €0.83 billion. EUDP is focused on demonstration projects while INNO-CCUS is focused on knowledge. EUDP provides:

- €10.15 million to the Bifrost project for the 2022-2023 period⁹⁰;
- €1.29 million to Project Greensand Phase 1 for the 2020-2021 period⁹¹; and
- €26.42 million to Project Greensand Phase 2 for the 2021-2023 period⁹².

The seismic acquisition of the eight chosen on-/near shore structures conducted by the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland had an approximate cost of €28 million and was funded by the yearly Danish agreement for funding for research and science under the Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science.

1.8.7 Sweden

Sweden has two main programmes available for R&I projects for CCS and CCU: Industriklivet run by the Swedish Energy agency and Klimatklivet run by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency^{93,94}.

Industriklivet has a budget of approximately €100 million per year and aims to decrease process emissions in industries such as cement, steel, and lime. The programme also focuses on negative emissions and provides support to both for research and investments. The aim is to make processes more efficient for technologies with a low TRL and to focus on emissions reductions for technologies with a high TRL. Innovation is an important selection factor. First of a Kind technologies are also supported and the programme tries to avoid a duplication of technologies. The programme finances capital expenditure and not operational expenditure. Basic research projects have two application dates across the year, while higher TRL projects can apply any time. This open-ended process is meant to take into account the need of industrial sites to shut down for maintenance during certain periods of the year.

Klimatklivet focuses on greenhouse gas emissions reduction and supports investments that would not be possible without state aid. Companies under the EU ETS cannot apply for this programme. Total support

⁸⁸ <https://inno-ccus.dk/2023/11/26/new-publication-maps-danish-ccus-research-and-innovation/>

⁸⁹ <https://ens.dk/en/our-responsibilities/research-development/eudp>

⁹⁰ <https://eudp.dk/en/node/16469>

⁹¹ <https://eudp.dk/en/node/16145>

⁹² <https://eudp.dk/en/node/16466>

⁹³ <https://www.industriklivet.se/>

⁹⁴ <https://www.naturvardsverket.se/amnesomraden/klimatomstallningen/klimatklivet/>

from this programme has amounted to SEK 13.3 billion or €1.18 billion. Measures supported by Klimatklivet are expected to contribute to an annual reduction of 2.5 million tonnes of greenhouse gas emissions during the period of operation (16 years on average). Funding is prioritised to measures that provide the greatest, lasting reduction in greenhouse gas emissions per SEK invested. Most of the investment costs for the various measures are borne by the applying organisation with Klimatklivet's funding share standing at 41% on average⁹⁵. CCS technologies compete with other technologies; the key selection factor is the emission reduction potential.

1.9 Summing up

1. A significant increase of the Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe is required to reach the targets set in the industrial carbon management strategy, the proposed EU 2040 climate target, and the proposed Net Zero Industry Act.
2. Existing EU funding mechanisms, and the cohesion between those, need to be improved to avoid a fragmented and incoherent funding approach.
3. A robust and stable EU ETS price is critical to guarantee sufficient funding availability for innovative CCS/CCU projects under the Innovation Fund.
4. The coordination/harmonisation of national selection criteria for R&D projects under the Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) could be useful for effective R&I efforts on climate technologies, including CCS/CCU.
5. Synergies between the CETP and Mission Innovation (MI) could have value, including by allowing MI countries to join future CETP calls in 2025.
6. Germany's Energieforschungsprogramm represent a strong opportunity for R&D funding for CCS/CCU. This opportunity should be fulfilled in the next programme rounds.

⁹⁵ <https://www.naturvardsverket.se/amnesomraden/klimatomstallningen/klimatklivet/resultat-for-klimatklivet/>